

Simulating the Role of RAD51 Over-Expression on DNA Repair and its Potential Impact on Tumor Prognosis via Targeted Gene Therapy

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Abstract

ROS-induced DNA damage is particularly detrimental in the context of cancers as the tumor microenvironment (TME) is often characterized by oxidative stress. Cells in the TME play a vital role in cancer pathogenesis, and by understanding the therapeutic strategies for cancer, ROS-induced damage can be mitigated to improve tumor prognosis. ROS can cause single-strand DNA breaks (SSBs) and double-strand breaks (DSBs); accumulating these breaks can lead to genomic instability and cancer progression. The study focuses on the pathway and effects of introducing DNA repair proteins (RAD51 in this study) via adenoviral vectors into the TME to reduce ROS-induced DNA damage. RAD51 is a repair protein involved with homologous recombination to anneal DSBs. Adenoviruses are double-stranded DNA viruses ubiquitous in common diseases like rhinitis; however, they are commonly used in clinical gene therapies. A gene therapy methodology that simulates adenoviral gene insertion without involving the actual virus focuses instead on engineered vectors designed for therapy. The DNA damage response efficacy can be measured by analyzing phosphorylated H2AX (γ H2AX), a histone that regulates DNA damage response. γ H2AX also plays a vital role in accumulating DNA repair proteins at the site of the break. During DSB induction, kinase enzymes phosphorylate many H2AX molecules that flank the break region – DSBs and γ H2AX increase analogously. If future preclinical studies confirm the effectiveness of this research, it could lead to significant benefits for patients, such as reducing their resistance to radiotherapy.

Keywords: ROS, tumor microenvironment, DNA repair proteins, RAD51, γ H2AX, adenoviral vectors

Introduction

This paper aims to explore gene therapy's impact on the prognosis of ROS-related tumors by enhancing DNA repair proteins within the TME. Given that ROS can induce DNA damage, this study aims to determine whether increasing the expression of DNA repair proteins through targeted gene therapy can improve treatment outcomes [1]. Part of the study was simulated on SnapGene, and the rest was completed by using addgene and SnapGene protocols as guidelines [2-8].

ROS

Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) are highly reactive chemicals formed from diatomic oxygen, water, and hydrogen peroxide; ROS are also effective signaling molecules [9]. Some common ROS are hydroperoxide, superoxide, and hydroxyl radicals. ROS are formed in all cells as a byproduct of cellular respiration [10]. Oxygen is the final electron acceptor in the

mitochondrial electron transport chain (ETC), and the final oxygen undergoes 4-electron reduction at cytochrome oxidase to form two water molecules [9]. 99% of all mitochondrial oxygen undergoes 4-electron reduction; however, less than 1% undergoes single electron reduction, yielding a ROS superoxide [11].

ROS in Cancer

Tumor cells and normal unaffected somatic cells both produce ROS [12-13]. However, the rate of ROS production is significantly elevated in tumor cells because tumor cells have an increased metabolic rate and exist in hypoxia. Tumors carry out the increased metabolism via the Warburg Effect: a phenomenon where cancer cells produce energy from glycolysis and lactic acid fermentation [14]. Relative hypoxia is a state of oxygen deficiency at the cellular level, and all solid tumors are subject to its effects. Hypoxia affects the cells' oxygen-reliant pathways as the electron transport chain is disrupted when the mitochondria are missing their final electron acceptors [15]. Without the final electron acceptor, built-up electrons partially reduce oxygen molecules and produce ROS. Tumor cells often exist in hypoxia, and the Warburg effect allows cancer cells to survive and proliferate in an oxygen-deficient environment.

ROS Damage on DNA

The resulting increase in ROS can be particularly detrimental to DNA by inducing DNA single-strand breaks (SSBs). One way this occurs is the production of an oxidative lesion (8-oxo-guanine or 8-oxoG) or thymine glycol [16]. Oxidative lesions occur when hydroxyl radicals oxidize the respective base. When DNA polymerase encounters an oxidative lesion, it may mistakenly add an adenine opposite of the 8-oxoG.

The cell may undergo carcinogenesis if this point mutation occurs in oncogenes, tumor suppressor genes, or stability genes. During base excision repair (BER), if the AP endonuclease protein improperly nicks the DNA to remove the 8-oxoG, it will lead to a single-strand break (SSB). If ROS simultaneously attacks opposing DNA strands by introducing DNA lesions, then the SSB accumulation will lead to a DNA double-stranded break (DSB) – which is more difficult to deal with. Thymine glycol lesions occur when thymine derivatives have unorthodox binding to their adenine counterparts. The thymine glycols cause DNA double helix distortions, leading to stalling of DNA polymerase during replication. The stalling can lead to the replication fork collapsing, and the formation of SSBs and DSBs if not dealt with appropriately [17]. Past studies have shown that thymine glycol is lethal in in vivo cell cultures [17-18]. Issues with DNA transcription arise due to the blocked DNA polymerase; transcription errors are one of the most common causes of carcinogenesis.

Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2) causes DNA damage by producing hydroxyl radicals when it reacts with chromatin-bound iron ions [19]. The Fenton Reaction is the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide via ferrous ion catalysts to produce hydroxyl radicals: ferrous catalysts are iron (II) or iron (III) [20]. The hydroxyl radicals released from the reaction can attack DNA, causing strand breaks and base modifications.

In summary, tumor cells produce more ROS due to increased metabolism (Warburg Effect) and relative hypoxia, leading to degraded mitochondrial function and increased ROS levels. ROS induces SSBs and oxidative lesions, leading to potential carcinogenesis. H_2O_2 is a common ROS that can cause DNA damage by producing hydroxyl molecules via the Fenton reaction, especially in the presence of iron ions.

ROS Affecting the Tumor Microenvironment

ROS significantly impacts the tumor microenvironment (TME) by promoting genetic instability, altering cellular behavior, and supporting tumor progression and metastasis through its effects on fibroblasts and immune cells. Cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) are key players in cancer initiation, progression, and metastasis. CAFs can be fibroblasts or myofibroblasts; alpha-smooth muscle actin-positive myofibroblasts are the most common populations of CAFs in tumors. CAFs are distinguished actors in tumor progression because the populations on the edge of tumors play a vital role in *in vivo* cancer progression [21].

ROS influences the differentiation of stem cells into CAFs in various ways. For instance, ROS can activate signaling pathways in the TME. ROS enhances the expression of cytokine TGF- β (cytokine involved in differentiating fibroblasts into CAFs) by increasing the activation of TGF- β ligands and receptors [22]. Furthermore, ROS has been shown to inhibit phosphatases that normally suppress TGF- β signaling, resulting in prolonged activation of the TGF- β pathway. Increased activation and prolongation of the TGF- β pathway yield increased CAFs in the tumor microenvironment. Weinberg et. al. co-cultured breast cancer cells with CAFs to show the effects of hydrogen peroxide (ROS) on CAFs [23]. Their results showed CAV-1 downregulation and increased expression of myofibroblast biomarkers. CAV-1 is a tumor suppressor protein, and its downregulation yields further tumorigenesis [24]. In their conclusion, ROS could alter the CAF phenotype to create a pro-tumorigenic microenvironment.

Different levels of ROS in the TME are called cytostatic and cytotoxic. Cytostatic (low levels of ROS) is characterized by transcriptional regulation and normal cellular activity, whereas cytotoxic (high levels of ROS) is marked by immune degradation and apoptosis [46]. Thus, for tumors to promote carcinogenesis and angiogenesis, they must ensure that ROS levels remain within a range that supports tumor growth and survival.

CAFs affect the DNA of cells in the TME by secreting growth factors (EGF and HGF), cytokines (e.g. IL-6, IL-8), chemokines, and ROS [25]. These secretions can induce DNA damage and promote genomic instability in nearby cells. The increased CAFs from ROS signaling will result in increased CAF secretions and DNA damage [26]. Studies have shown that EGFR signaling leads to an increased level of intracellular ROS. As IL-8 transactivation directly increases EGFR expression, CAF-excreted IL-8 increases intracellular ROS production [26-29].

Tumor-originating ROS can affect the TME because the ROS directly spreads into the TME. Another way tumor cells release ROS into the TME is via exosomes [23]. Exosomes are extracellular vesicles (EVs) made of a phospholipid bilayer; exosomes also contain various biomolecules [30]. EV contents are released into the cytosol of their target cells. As mentioned previously, CAV-1 downregulation is a stark characteristic of many ROS-cancers; CAV-1 downregulation results in increased exosomal uptake of stromal cells. Paggetti et. al. showed that chronic lymphatic leukemia-derived (CLL) exosomes, caused stromal cells in the TME to exhibit phenotypic properties characteristic of CAFs [31]. The affected stromal cells showed increased proliferation, migration, and secretion of tumor-supportive cytokines – resulting in tumor progression. Increased ROS leads to increased exosomal uptake; therefore, more exosomal cells will express CAF characteristics.

In summary, ROS promotes genetic instability and facilitates tumorigenesis by affecting fibroblasts and immune cells in the TME. ROS enhances TGF- β signaling, which leads to the differentiation of CAFs. CAFs are fibroblasts or myofibroblasts that can induce tumorigenesis. Cytostatic ROS levels support homeostatic cell function, whereas cytotoxic ROS levels cause

apoptosis; tumors can maintain ROS levels to support growth and survival. CAFs cause DNA damage by secreting growth factors, cytokines, chemokines, and ROS. Tumors can directly release ROS into the TME via exosomes, which induces CAF phenotype in stromal cells. CAV-1 downregulation results in increased exosomal uptake and a tumorigenic TME.

Approach

If we limit the ROS damage to the DNA of cells in the TME, we can prevent the excessive proliferation of CAFs. A lower amount of CAFs would result in fewer tumorigenic secretions, leading to a slower rate of carcinogenesis. Also, limiting ROS damage can prevent the overexpression of CAFs by reducing exosomal uptake. Thus, this study designs and outlines a gene therapy approach that uses adenoviral vectors with RAD51, a DNA repair protein. The study focuses on the molecular cloning method to generate an ideal adenoviral vector from the pAMHDA_{GT8-4} adenoviral plasmid. RAD51 – a DNA repair protein that anneals DSBs – is the gene proposed for insertion into the designed adenoviral plasmid. RAD51 may improve the efficacy of existing cancer therapies by hindering tumor progression.

Data

Figure 1. pAMHDAdGT8-4 Gene Sequence. PspXI (restriction site on nucleotide position 7666) and KpnI (restriction site on nucleotide position 4505) are the restriction enzymes marked.

Figure 2. Adenoviral-RAD51-eGFP plasmid after pAMHDAdGT8-4 digestion reaction. eGFP (green) and RAD51 (orange) were inserted into the location of the lacZ gene, between the SV40 poly (A) signal and mCMV promoter.

Figure 3. Electrophoresis Simulation Results. The agarose gel's result **simulation ran on SnapGene**. The schematic for the electrophoresis reaction ran to measure the accuracy of the digestion reaction. A 1kb DNA ladder was added to the unmarked lane; lane 1 contains the undigested pAMHDA_{GT8-4} plasmid; lane 2 contains only the lacZ gene fragment; and lane 3 has the KpNI and PsPXI digested pAMHDA_{GT8-4}.

Figure 4. Predicted Western Blot. The 1kb plus DNA ladder (NEB #N3200S) was used as a standard for protein molecule weight (in kDa). Lanes 1 and 2 contain cell lysates from cells subject to oxidative stress. Lane 1 contains β -actin and γ H2AX, while Lane 2 contains β -actin, adenoviral RAD51, and γ H2AX. β -actin is used as a loading control antibody to ensure that protein loading is uniform across the lanes. β -actin expression was consistent in both lanes. Lane 2 had high RAD51 and low γ -HA2X expression; γ H2AX expression is expected at a higher intensity than RAD51. RAD51 was expressed at 37-38 kDa, γ H2AX at 15 kDa, and β -actin at 42 kDa. **It should be noted that in a real Western Blot, bands would not be identical. Bands were made identical for illustrative purposes—allowing readers to focus on the conceptual understanding.**

Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E. Value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
1380	1380	100%	0.00	100.00%	9912	Query_606289

Figure 5. The BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) result showed that 100% of the query sequence was identical to a part of the subject sequence. The RAD51 sequence was inserted as the query, and the experimental pAMHDAAdGT8-4 sequence (Figure 2) was inserted as the subject.

Methods

Simulation

Restriction Enzyme Digestion Reaction and Gibson Assembly were simulated via SnapGene's features. Other processes were outlined using SnapGene or addgene protocols [2-8].

Cell lines and tissue culture

The HEK 293T cell line used in the study was obtained from MilliPore Sigma. Cells were derived from human fetal kidney cells. An adherent cell line that expresses the SV40 large T antigen. They are shipped on dry ice and require storage at -196 C. The cell line is competent for vector replication with SV 40 origin of replication. The line is favorable for tissue culture transfection and DNA replication. HEK 293T is used for large-scale vector production. The culture medium needed consists of DMEM, 2 mM glutamine, and 10 % Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS).

The Human Lung Carcinoma Cell Line (A549) that was proposed in this study was derived from the lung tissues of a 58-year-old Caucasian male with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) in 1972; it was from an adenocarcinoma of the human alveolar basal epithelial cells. A549 cells are ubiquitous in ROS-related studies [32].

Restriction Enzyme Digestion Reaction

Digestion reaction involved cutting the lacZ gene at excision sites KpNI and PspXI in plasmid pAMHDAAdGT8-4 (addgene plasmid 26421). Each restriction enzyme only has one specific excision site in the plasmid (Figure 1). In a microcentrifuge, a combination of the following would be added: 1 ug of adenoviral plasmid, 1x CutSmart buffer, 1μL of KpNI enzyme, 1μl of PspXI enzyme, and nuclease-free water to bring the total volume to 20 μl [2]. The 1x CutSmart buffer compatibility was determined for both enzymes based on the NEBuffer restriction enzymes chart. The reaction would incubate at 37°C for 1 hour to excise the lacZ fragment sequence.

Gel Purification

The 1% agarose gel would be prepared by mixing 1g agarose powder, 100 ml 1x TAE buffer, and 10 μl Syber Safe or EtBr [3]. After the solution solidifies, 5 μl DNA ladder, 200 ng of the lacZ gene, the wildtype pAMHDAAdGT8-4 sequence, and the pAMHDAAdGT8-4 digested fragments would be loaded into their respective lanes. Electrophoresis was simulated via the SnapGene electrophoresis simulation feature. The gel purification simulation shows no unnecessary or abnormal bands: the digestion reaction was successful (Figure 3).

Gibson Assembly Method

Gibson Assembly is a molecular cloning method that joins DNA fragments in an isothermal reaction. The RAD51-eGFP gene block sequence is a sequence that has at least 25 bp homology with the adenoviral backbone at each end. The sequence could be ordered through Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT company). The designed RAD51-eGFP fragment would be inserted between the mCMV promoter and SV40 poly(A)tail signal (Figure 2). The Gibson Assembly Master Mix contains exonuclease, DNA polymerase, and DNA ligase. RAD51-eGFP fragments and the purified adenoviral backbone vector are combined until they are in the range of 0.03-0.5 pmol and a ratio of 1:2 (insert: vector) [4]. Finally, the reaction would be incubated at 50°C for 60 minutes – yielding a continuous DNA molecule.

Bacterial Transformation

Bacterial transformation is the process by which bacteria incorporate foreign DNA into their genomes. 5 µl Gibson mix would be added to 25µl Stellar cells (a high-efficiency E. coli strain) in a test tube, incorporating the completed plasmid into the Stellar genome. The test tube would be put on ice for 20 minutes, then heat shocked for 30 seconds at 42°C. The Stellar cells and Gibson mix would then be recovered in 200 µl Lysogeny Broth (LB, a nutrient-rich medium that supports the growth of bacteria) media for 30 minutes at 37°C. After bacterial cells had recovered, 200µl aliquots of the transformed cells would be spread on the LB-Amp plate. The plate would be incubated face-downward for 16 hours at 37°C. Each colony that grows on the plate is one correct plasmid.

Inoculating bacterial culture

A colony would be resuspended in 5 mL LB media containing 1x ampicillin antibiotic and grown for 14 hours at 37°C with 250 rpm shaking [5]. Transformation of the DNA is vital for the amplification of the DNA.

Miniprep to prepare the adenoviral vector plasmid

The plasmid amplified from the colony can be purified by Monarch[®] Plasmid DNA Miniprep Kit (NEB #T1010). The inoculating bacterial culture would be centrifuged at 16,000xg for 30 seconds. The supernatant must be discarded before the cell pellet can be resuspended in 200 µL Plasmid Resuspension Buffer B1. Resuspended cells would be lysed with 200 µL Plasmid Lysis Buffer B2. The lysed cells are neutralized by adding 400 µL Plasmid Neutralization Buffer B3. The cell lysate would be clarified by centrifuging for 2-5 minutes at 16,000xg. Approximately 800 µL of supernatant would be transferred to a miniprep column (containing a silica filter for purifying nucleic acids) and centrifuged for 1 minute. The flow-through would be discarded. The DNA bound to the silica matrix would be eluted in 30 µL of nuclease-free water through centrifugation, resulting in ready-to-use purified plasmids.

Sanger sequencing would be completed to check whether the genetic insert in the adenoviral vector was correctly incorporated and matched the expected sequence. The sequencing reaction mixtures would be created by combining the following: denatured original DNA sequence, a sequencing primer, DNA polymerase, deoxynucleotide triphosphates (dNTPs), and dideoxynucleotide triphosphates (ddNTPs). The PCR reaction with this mixture results in fluorescently labeled oligonucleotides (DNA fragments with 2-100 nucleotides). DNA fragments would then be separated based on size via capillary gel electrophoresis. As fragments exit the capillary tube, the fluorescent dyes are illuminated by a laser beam and detected by a

photomultiplier. Different DNA fragments emit light at varying wavelengths; therefore, discrete colors and peaks are visible on the chromatogram.

Making adenovirus in human embryonic kidney 293 cells (HEK 293T)

The BLAST sequencing would be used to show that the incorporated RAD51 insert was identical to its counterpart in the completed adenoviral vector. An example of using BLAST to assess the alignment of cloned RAD51 and the expected adenoviral vector is shown in Figure 5.

Once the adenoviral vector sequence was confirmed, this design plasmid would be transfected into HEK 293T cells. 1 mL of culture mix would be added to 9 mL of fresh media resulting in a 1:10 split that grows in two days; after two days, the plate would be expected to have 80-85% confluency. Trypsin would be added to the plate, and cells would be split. A 1:1 ratio with 20 uL total volume of cell culture and trypan blue would be added in a 1.7 mL Eppendorf tube. The cell concentration, 2×10^6 cells/mL would be counted via an automated cell QuadCounter.

A 6-well plate would be the best option as it provided ample surface area (9.6 cm²) for the cells to grow—ensuring a consistent and uniform transfection efficiency. To produce the virus, 600,000 cells would be required. 2 mL fresh media would be added to each well, and the plate would be incubated in the TC incubator for 24 hours. Cell confluence would be around 60-80% the next day.

Approximately 24 hours before transfection, the Opti-MEM and *TransIT-LT1* Reagent (which ensures high-efficiency plasmid delivery in mammalian cells) would need to warm to room temperature. 250µl Opti-MEM Reduced-Serum Medium and 2.5ug plasmid DNA would be added to a sterile tube. 7.5µl *TransIT-LT1* Reagent would be added to the diluted DNA mixture, avoiding cross-contamination between the *TransIT-LT1* Reagent and the plastic tube. The solution would be incubated at room temperature for 15 minutes after mixing with a pipet [6].

Finally, the *TransIT-LT1* Reagent (prepared in the previous step) would be added dropwise to different areas of the wells. The culture vessel would be gently shaken to evenly distribute the *TransIT-LT1* Reagent DNA complexes. After 24 hours of incubation, the growth medium should be replaced with a fresh medium. Around 2 mL of cell lysate would be harvested from the transfection process on Day 2-3 post-transfection. The produced adenovirus can be checked by examining the RAD51-GFP under a fluorescence microscope and measuring the GFP (Green Fluorescence Protein) signal.

Adenoviral vector transfection in lung carcinoma cells (A549)

HEK 293T adenovirus cells on ice would be thawed and briefly mixed before usage. 10µl 1000X polybrene (facilitates viral absorption and viral entry) would be added to 1 mL aliquot of virus. The adenoviral mix would be added to a 6-well plate containing A549 cells. The first sample would serve as a control group and not receive any virus. The second sample would receive 250 µL of the virus, while the third sample would receive 750 µL of the virus. Each sample would be gently mixed and placed back into the incubator; the media would be exchanged after 5 hours. The viability of cells should be checked on Day 3 after infection. The infection would be assessed based on GFP expression on Day 4.

Flow Cytometry

Flow Cytometry is a technique used to analyze the physical and chemical characteristics of cell particles as they flow in a stream through a laser light source. The complete adenoviral cells would be stained and passed through a nozzle surrounded by sheath fluid. The light that passes through the stained cells would be detected and quantified to measure the accuracy of adenoviral creation [7]. Thus, the successful infected cells would result in a GFP-positive cell population.

Oxidative Stress Induction in Cell Culture

Post-transfection A549 cells would be treated at 90% confluency with hydrogen peroxide to induce oxidative stress. 200 μ L hydrogen peroxide would be prepared in a complete growth medium. The medium in each well would be replaced with the 3 mmol hydrogen peroxide, and the cells would incubate for 2 hours. The medium would be aspirated, and the cells would be washed with PBS to remove residual hydrogen peroxide. The cells would be allowed to rest in a complete growth medium for 24 hours.

Western Blot

A western blot would measure the expression of RAD51 and γ H2AX in the adenoviral cells (Figure 4). Adenoviral cells would be lysed and added to a falcon tube. The cell homogenate would be centrifuged at increasing speeds, with the supernatant being transmitted intermittently. Proteins would be extracted, and 40 ug total proteins of each sample would be prepared to run on a 12% SDS-PAGE.

The 12% SDS-PAGE would be cast with the following ingredients: 30 % Acrylamide-Bis 37/5:1, TEMED, water, 10 % SDS, 10 % AP, lower buffer (0.5 M Tris, pH 8.8), and upper buffer (1.5 M Tris, ph 6.8). The lower solution would be used to cast the resolving gel. Isopropanol would be added on top of the resolving gel layer for 15-30 minutes. Isopropanol would be discarded after the resolving solution is solidified. The upper gel solution and comb are inserted on top of the resolving gel and incubated at room temperature for 15 minutes until it is solidified [8].

SDS loading dye would be added to a 40 ug protein sample at 1x concentration. The lanes would be loaded according to Figure 4. Beta-actin (β -actin), a protein with a molecular weight of 42 kDa, is a reference marker to facilitate the clear differentiation and analysis of target proteins.

Proteins would be transferred to polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes to enhance subsequent detection and quantification. PVDF membranes would be probed with appropriate primary antibodies and then incubated with anti-rabbit IgG and HRP-linked secondary antibodies.

Results

The study aimed to design an adenoviral vector packaging RAD51 for pre-clinical tests to reduce ROS-induced DNA damage. Molecular cloning techniques instruction for how to insert the RAD51 gene into the pAMHDA_{GT8-4} adenoviral backbone was proposed. If future preclinical studies prove the efficacy of this proposed methodology, then RAD51 insertion would be a viable method to inhibit cancer progression in the TME.

Techniques and processes were completed with either SnapGene or outlined with addgene and SnapGene protocols. The restriction digestion reaction was done to excise the lacZ gene from the pAMHDAAdGT8-4 adenoviral backbone using the restriction enzymes KpNI and PspXI. The gel purification would be done to purify the digested adenoviral backbone. Simulated electrophoresis confirmed precise cutting at the restriction sites with no additional bands (Figure 3).

Gibson Assembly aimed to insert the RAD51-eGFP sequences into the adenoviral vector between the mCMV promoter and the SV40 poly(A) tail (Figure 2). Gibson Assembly ligated the RAD51-eGFP sequences into the adenoviral backbone. During incubation, the 5' overhangs would be removed with exonuclease to create single-stranded 3' overhangs. The complementary single-stranded regions anneal to each other, while DNA polymerase fills in the gaps; DNA ligase seals the nicks to ensure a continuous circular DNA plasmid.

Bacterial transformation introduced the recombinant plasmid DNA into Stellar E. coli cells to amplify the plasmids containing the RAD51 gene. Ampicillin medium was selected to ensure that the grown bacteria had the adenoviral-RAD51-eGFP plasmid containing the ampicillin-resistant gene. The growth of the colonies means that the E. coli cells were able to successfully uptake the recombinant plasmids, with each colony representing a correct circular adenoviral-RAD51-eGFP plasmid. The single colony would be inoculated in ampicillin LB-medium for 12-16 hours and the E. coli would replicate and transcribe more adenoviral plasmids every 20 minutes.

Miniprep isolated the synthesized adenoviral plasmid from the LB-Amp culture, and Sanger sequencing can be used to verify the correct insertion of RAD51. Post-sequencing, BLAST tools can be used to assess the cloning design by aligning the Sanger sequencing result with the expected adenoviral sequence. BLAST should show no mismatches or mutations in the RAD51 gene sequence during the cloning process (Figure 5). HEK 293T cells would be used as host cells to produce adenovirus particles. The high transfection efficiency of the cells yields a high success rate of producing adenoviral particles with the desired gene of interest. These adenoviral particles would be transfected to A549 cells. A549 cells are qualified for the insertion of plasmids as they possess the SV 40 sequence.

The infection efficiency would be monitored by assessing GFP expression. GFP fluorescence would be visible in the transfected cells on Day 4 — indicating a successful transduction. Flow cytometry was employed to quantify the transduction efficiency by measuring GFP expression in A549. The analysis would show a range of GFP fluorescence intensities that reflected the varying levels of adenoviral transduction.

The results from the expected Western blot indicate that when RAD51 levels are increased, the γ H2AX concentration decreases (Figure 4). The γ H2AX1, which indicates an increase in DSBs, was highly expressed in the untreated lane, where the cell lysate would be exposed to oxidative stress without RAD51 supplementation. In contrast, the addition of RAD51 resulted in a decrease in the number of DSBs. Furthermore, γ H2AX is expected at a higher intensity than RAD51 as it has a higher nTPM (transcripts per million) in A549 cells. The γ H2AX has 88.3 nTPM, whereas RAD51 only has 19.4 nTPM (data collected from *Human Protein Atlas*).

Discussion

The preclinical analysis demonstrates that RAD51 insertion into the pAMHDA_{GT8-4} adenoviral backbone is feasible and effective. P53 is a tumor suppressor protein that plays a role in DNA repair, apoptosis, and cell cycle regulation. The p53 gene has been successfully inserted into adenoviral vectors, resulting in tumor regression and growth arrests [33]. Various gene sequences encoding proteins with diverse functions have been successfully inserted into an adenoviral plasmid – reinforcing the viability of RAD51 insertion [31].

Successful RAD51 insertion into cells in the TME could allow for localized repair and tumor control. A key aspect of tumor control is tumor growth inhibition and metastasis prevention. Preventing metastasis is a thoroughly explored route for cancer treatment: angiogenesis treatments prevent metastasis by inhibiting new blood vessel formation [34]. RAD51 improves genomic stability by dissuading a tumorigenic environment.

RAD51 can repair DSBs, and its efficacy can be measured with the γ H2AX biomarker. Phosphorylated H2AX (γ H2AX) increases analogously with DSBs [35]. γ H2AX functions by forming cohesions around the sites of DSBs: it holds loose DNA ends together, allowing for repair to occur [36]. If RAD51 effectively facilitates the homologous recombination of DSBs, then the number of γ H2AX foci will decrease. The theoretical Western blot detects high levels of γ H2AX in lane 2 (lane lacking RAD51 infection). High levels of γ H2AX suggest ineffective repair. Whereas, in lane 1 a reduction in γ H2AX signals can be linked to successful homologous recombination via RAD51 insertion (Figure 4).

If future studies demonstrate the viability of this gene therapy approach, then patients can reap many benefits. Researchers have shown that tumors with steady genomes are less likely to develop resistance to treatments like radiotherapy [37]. Therefore, successfully repairing DNA via RAD51 insertion, will result in cancer cells with more stable genomes. Radiotherapy kills tumor cells by indirectly inducing DNA damage via ROS creation [38]. Free radicals are formed when high-energy radiation interacts with water molecules in the TME [38-39]. As previously discussed, elevated levels of ROS can induce DSBs, potentially enhancing the tumorigenic potential of the TME. Radiotherapy increases the likelihood of gene mutations by creating selection pressure on cancer cells: it kills the majority of cells but potentially leaves behind those with inherited resistance. By decreasing the frequency of resistant cells emerging through mutations, RAD51-mediated repair could result in enhanced genomic stability, potentially reducing the likelihood of radiotherapy resistance. Stability can increase the efficacy of radiotherapy and improve the prognosis of patients.

Conclusion

In conclusion, RAD51 insertion into the TME is a possible avenue for future cancer treatment. The findings suggest that RAD51 insertion into the pAMHDA_{GT8-4} adenoviral backbone can potentially enhance genomic stabilization in the TME. RAD51 insertion could pave the way for new gene therapy strategies in cancer treatment by reducing tumor progression and radiotherapy resistance.

Future research should focus on in vivo studies to confirm these findings and assess the long-term effects of RAD51 insertion. In vivo studies would help researchers more accurately understand the implications of RAD51 upregulation in the TME. Studies on long-term effects would demonstrate the durability of therapeutic effects and the possibility of consequences.

Limitations

However, it must be noted that further research must be done before the clinical use of adenoviral vectors with RAD51. These results should be interpreted cautiously as the study was hypothesized based on a literature review and SnapGene simulations. A simulation of an in vitro study may not account for external confounding variables that may impede the results.

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Signature of Lead Author:

A handwritten signature in blue ink on a light-colored background. The signature is highly stylized and cursive, featuring a large, sweeping initial letter that resembles an 'A' or 'S'. The rest of the signature consists of several horizontal strokes and loops, making it difficult to decipher. There are two small dots below the main signature.